

Towards Evaluating Image Recommendations in Digital News and Media Ecosystem

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Abstract—The News and Media landscape has undergone significant transformations in recent years, driven by the rise of new technologies and the widespread use of social media. This evolution introduces unique challenges for professionals working within this environment (e.g., journalists, content creators, and news authors), with a major one being the efficient sourcing of images that complement article content. In response to this challenge, we developed VIREO, a tool that recommends images based on textual content. In this paper, we make a step towards the practical effectiveness of VIREO’s core models in recommending images for real-world articles, with a specific focus on image recommendation efficiency. Our results indicate that VIREO offers a promising solution for professionals seeking to meet the evolving demands of the News and Media landscape while maintaining content quality and engagement.

Index Terms—artificial intelligence, machine learning, image recommendation, image analysis, BLIP model, language-image pre-training

I. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of new technologies and the growth of social media have caused changes in the media ecosystem in recent years. People who work in it, such as journalists, content creators, authors, and news professionals, face new challenges in this environment, which is constantly changing. Several requirements in the media sector have arisen due to the growth of alternative news sources, such as social media being the leading news source, particularly for younger people. One of them is the necessity to post content as soon as possible on various platforms, combining text and visuals to reach the target audience. Combining text and visuals (i.e., news articles with appropriate images) raises the readers’ interest in the news and improves engagement. Hence, media professionals adapt their publication strategies to meet these requirements and match the consumers’ expectations.

Considering that several tools that support cross-posting (e.g., Planable, eClincher, Buffer, and Hootsuite, are available in the market and save time and that professionals in the News and Media industry (e.g., journalists) have quick access to new information which they can check against fake news, hoaxes, and scams (e.g., eufactcheck.eu, IFCN, Google fact check tools, FactCheck.org), the challenge is to quickly find images that match the article content. Aiming to meet this challenge, we developed the VIREO tool [1], which recommends image(s) based on text (e.g., article content). Using VIREO,

media professionals create visually appealing and engaging stories in less time.

In this paper, we seek to evaluate the practical effectiveness of VIREO’s core models in recommending images for real-world articles. Specifically, our research question is: “*How well do the core models of VIREO perform in recommending images that align with the content of real-life articles, with a focus on image recommendation efficiency?*”. The remainder of the paper is as follows: we present the background and related work; next, we present the method and the results of the experiment; finally, we discuss the implications, limitations, and future steps of our work.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. VIREO framework

Recent research raises the importance of providing tools to summarize news articles and related images using artificial intelligence (AI) techniques. Although they follow reliable methods, their performance and maturity levels are limited [2, 3]; therefore, there is room for improvement. The most common challenges in such works include the natural language understanding (NLU) to capture text concepts other than general [3–5] and the accurate image suggestion, focusing on eye-catching visual content that expresses diverse states (e.g., appealing, surprising, polarization, positive/negative emotional states) [6–8]. The VIREO [1] framework overcomes these challenges through a 3-step process: i) understanding and representation of article content (textual content) in a machine-readable and understandable format, ii) generation of image caption embeddings, and iii) accurate and fast image recommendations. The conceptual architecture of the VIREO framework (Fig. 1) consists of three main modules: i) Article Analysis module that uses natural language processing (NLP) techniques (e.g., tokenization, part-of-speech tagging, and named entity recognition) to analyze the text and extract relevant information; ii) Image Analysis module that uses computer vision techniques (e.g., feature extraction and image classification) to analyze the images and extract relevant information; iii) Image Matching and Recommendation modules that use AI techniques to match the images to the text and recommend appropriate images to accompany the provided article. Raptis et al. [1] provide a detailed description of the VIREO framework and its modules.

Fig. 1. Conceptual architecture of the VIREO framework [1].

B. BLIP model

The core Image Analysis module of VIREO is based on BLIP [9], a novel vision-language pre-training (VLP) framework. BLIP reports an increased performance in vision-language understanding and generation tasks, which makes it versatile for various multimodal downstream tasks. Unlike many methods that heavily rely on noisy data for pre-training, BLIP leverages this data by introducing two components: a captioner, which generates synthetic captions for images, and a filter, which removes noisy captions from the original texts and the synthetic ones. By bootstrapping captions and improving the dataset quality, BLIP achieves high-performance results in a wide range of vision-language tasks, including image-text retrieval, image captioning, and visual question answering. Additionally, BLIP demonstrates strong zero-shot generalization to video-language tasks, and thus, it is considered a promising advancement in multimodal AI. Hence, BLIP introduces several advantages, including flexibility in task domains, noise reduction, zero-shot generalization, diverse synthetic captioning, and efficient pre-training [10], which has led to its wide adoption in image analysis research [11–13] as it reports higher performance scores than other related models, such as LXMERT, UNITER, and SOHO [9].

The next section discusses the concepts of vision-language pre-training, knowledge distillation, and data augmentation, which, along with the characteristics of the BLIP model, are fundamental tools of the Image Analysis module of the VIREO framework.

C. Vision-language pre-training, knowledge distillation, and data augmentation

Vision-language pre-training represents an approach aimed at enhancing the performance of downstream tasks in both vision and language domains. This is achieved by pre-training models using vast image-text pairs [13]. However, a significant challenge in this process arises due to the high cost of obtaining human-annotated texts [14]. To address this, most methods utilize image and alt-text pairs sourced (e.g., from the web), despite noise in this data, even with rule-based filters [15]. The benefits of dataset scaling often overshadow the detrimental effects of this noise. Such vision and language tasks encompass understanding-based objectives like image-text retrieval and generation-based objectives like image cap-

tioning. The multimodal mixture of encoder-decoder models, like BLIP, offers enhanced flexibility and performance across a broad spectrum of downstream tasks while maintaining a simple and efficient pre-training approach.

Knowledge distillation enhances the performance of a ‘student’ model by transferring knowledge from a ‘teacher’ model. Within knowledge distillation, self-distillation is a special case where both the teacher and student models are of equal sizes. Notably, self-distillation has proven effective in improving image classification tasks [16] and in vision-language pre-training [17]. Models like BLIP provide unique strategies in vision-language pre-training. Instead of requiring the student model to produce the same class predictions as the teacher, they take more effective routes. An example of such an approach is that the captioner distills its knowledge by generating semantically rich synthetic captions, while the filter refines its knowledge by eliminating noisy captions. This innovative perspective knowledge distillation sets the stage for improved model performance.

Although data augmentation has gained widespread acceptance within computer vision, its application in language-related tasks is not as straightforward. In recent years, there has been a notable shift toward utilizing generative language models for synthesizing examples across various NLP tasks [18–20]. While such methods have primarily focused on low-resource language tasks, current state-of-the-art [9] highlights a distinctive advantage. Such approaches showcase how the integration of synthetic captions can significantly benefit large-scale vision-language pre-training, setting their methods apart from the rest.

The afore challenges in vision-language pre-training, knowledge distillation, and data augmentation are addressed in the core modules of the Image Analysis module of the VIREO framework, based on the BLIP model.

III. EXPERIMENT

A. Methodology and setup

We conducted an experiment to address our research question (“*How well do the core models of VIREO perform in recommending images that align with the content of real-life articles, with a focus on image recommendation efficiency?*”), which focuses on assessing the performance of VIREO’s core models in recommending images that align with the content of real-life articles, with a specific emphasis on image recommendation efficiency. The steps and procedures of this experiment were:

- **Dataset creation.** To begin, we assembled a dataset comprising real-world articles, each accompanied by at least one corresponding image. To construct this dataset, we utilized the newsdata.io API to gather over 2,500 news articles spanning various domains, including but not limited to business, sports, science, and environment. The diverse range of article categories was chosen to ensure the dataset would encompass a broad spectrum of topics and content types. Fig. 3 depicts instances of the dataset.

Fig. 2. Example of chunking articles into textual and visual content.

- **Image analysis.** For the image analysis process, we applied VIREO’s Image Analysis module. Each image within the dataset underwent caption embedding generation using the BLIP model. This step was important for transforming image content into numerical representations, facilitating subsequent comparisons and recommendations.
- **Text analysis.** Each article’s text content was analyzed using BERT within VIREO’s Image Analysis module. BERT [21] is an NLP model that excels at understanding language in context, thanks to its bidirectional approach, setting new benchmarks and enabling remarkable performance in various language-related tasks. This step enabled us to capture the semantic nuances of the articles and derive textual representations that could be matched with the image embeddings.
- **Image recommendations.** We considered multiple recommendation scenarios to ensure a comprehensive assessment of image recommendation efficiency and mitigate potential biases. Specifically, we evaluated and recorded the best 1 to 12 images for each article. This approach aimed to provide a range of recommendations, avoiding the limitation of offering only a single image. The recommended image(s) is (are) evaluated against the original images accompanying the articles.

By applying this methodology, we aimed to evaluate the performance of VIREO’s core models in recommending images that align with the content of real-life articles. Analyzing the obtained recommendations provides insights about the effectiveness of VIREO’s core models in this context. This methodological approach implements a comprehensive and rigorous evaluation of the research question, ensuring a validated assessment of image recommendation efficiency while considering real-world article content.

B. Results

The results of our experiment provided evidence about the efficiency of VIREO’s core models in recommending images that align with the content of real-life articles. Table I and Fig. 3 present the results for a different number of recommended images (1-12). The data demonstrates a clear trend in the performance of the recommendation system as the number of images suggested increases. Notably, when the system offered only one image, the recommendation accuracy was 11.24%. However, as the number of images recommended grew, so did the accuracy, reaching 56.24% when seven images were suggested. Beyond this point, the increase in accuracy tapers off, with the system plateauing at around 58.52% when recommending between eight and ten images. This is derived when applying Eq. 1 to find when the plateau starts. In the following equation, i represents the index at which the plateau starts, j is an index variable used to iterate through the data, P_{j+1} and P_j represent consecutive performance values, N_{j+1} and N_j represent consecutive number of recommended images, the condition $<$ checks if the absolute value of the rate of change of performance with respect to the number of recommended images is less than 0.01, and \min finds the minimum index j that satisfies this condition, and i is assigned that value.

$$i = \min\{j \mid \left| \frac{P_{j+1} - P_j}{N_{j+1} - N_j} \right| < 1e - 2\} \quad (1)$$

These results suggest that while the initial image recommendation might be less accurate, offering users a selection of images significantly improves alignment with the content of real-life articles. This observation is important for content recommendation systems, emphasizing the value of diversifying image suggestions to enhance user engagement and satisfaction with article-related visuals. The findings of this

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE OF VIREO PER NUMBER OF RECOMMENDED IMAGES

# Recommended images	# Matched images	Performance
1	256	11.24%
2	507	20.28%
3	844	33.76%
4	1068	42.72%
5	1238	49.52%
6	1294	51.76%
7	1406	56.24%
8	1409	56.36%
9	1463	58.52%
10	1469	58.76%
11	1492	59.68%
12	1493	59.72%

study provide valuable insights for further refinement and optimization of such recommendation systems.

Furthermore, the results of our study underscore the significance of providing users with multiple image recommendations rather than limiting them to a single choice. Providing users with a selection of images not only mitigates bias in the recommendation process but also empowers individuals to exercise their preferences and efficiently select the visual elements that best fit their interests. This approach aligns with human-centric design principles, enhancing the overall user experience and reducing the time required to find a personally appealing image. In a world where visual content plays an increasingly vital role, this user-centric approach contributes to more satisfying and engaging interactions, ultimately benefiting content consumers and recommendation systems. This insight emphasizes the importance of personalization and user agency in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of image recommendations within real-life articles.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this section, we discuss our work’s practical and theoretical implications, outline the limitations of the experiment we conducted, and provide suggestions for future research directions.

A. Implications

The findings of this study carry practical and theoretical implications for various fields, particularly in the News and Media sector, content recommendation, and artificial intelligence. The key practical implication centers on the potential for AI models, such as VIREO, BLIP, and BERT, to enhance content creation workflows. Media professionals, content creators, and news agencies can harness AI-driven tools like VIREO to streamline the process of recommending images that align with textual content. This AI-driven approach speeds up the content creation process and enhances its quality. It allows professionals to generate visually engaging stories efficiently, a precious asset in the fast-paced media landscape. By utilizing advanced AI models like BLIP and BERT, media professionals can fine-tune their content recommendations to suit the needs of their audiences better. While we did not perform a user study, we underscore the potential of AI

Fig. 3. Example of chunking articles into textual and visual content.

systems to offer personalized and relevant image suggestions, thereby enhancing the user experience. Organizations in the News and Media ecosystem can utilize such models to tailor their content to the preferences of their audience (e.g., readers and viewers), further improving engagement and satisfaction. These practical implications allow AI researchers to refine their models and incorporate such techniques into their vision-language pre-training methodologies.

Regarding the theoretical implications, the study highlights the role of AI, particularly vision-language models like BLIP, in enhancing content creation. AI-driven tools like VIREO are pivotal in helping journalists, content creators, and news professionals generate engaging stories by recommending images that align with textual content. This underscores the theoretical idea that AI can be a transformative force in optimizing content creation workflows, improving efficiency, and enhancing the overall quality of content. The results also emphasize shifting towards a more human-centric approach in AI systems. In particular, providing users with a choice of images reflects the importance of user-centric design principles. AI should not merely be about automation but also about empowering users to make informed choices. This aligns with the broader discourse on responsible and ethical AI development, prioritizing individual needs and preferences. The study takes advantage of knowledge distillation and data augmentation techniques, which are demonstrated in the core modules of the VIREO framework. These techniques are highlighted as promising strategies in vision-language pre-training. They offer flexibility, noise reduction, and improved performance in AI models. The theoretical implications extend to the AI research community, where these techniques can inspire further advancements in multimodal AI and enhance the quality of vision-language models.

B. Limitations

Our experiment has several limitations that should be noted. First, the image recommendations’ quality relies on the articles and images in our dataset. This means that if the original articles or accompanying images were of low quality or relevance, it could impact the accuracy of our evaluation. Second,

our experiment focused on the efficiency and alignment of image recommendations. However, it did not delve into the broader aspects of audience engagement and the impact of recommended images on users' behavior. Moreover, while diverse, our dataset's size may not fully represent the vast range of topics and content types found in the real-world News and Media landscape, potentially limiting the generalizability of our findings. Additionally, factors such as the quality and quantity of training data and model hyperparameters may influence the performance of VIREO's core models. Lastly, the dynamic nature of the News and Media landscape and the evolving nature of news articles and social media trends may challenge the long-term effectiveness of image recommendation models, which might not adapt swiftly to emerging content types or shifts in user preferences.

C. Future steps

As our study focused on the practical effectiveness of VIREO's core models in recommending images for real-world articles, there are several directions for future research and improvement: i) further investigation could explore the integration of user engagement metrics to assess how recommended images impact audience interaction with news articles; this could involve conducting user studies to understand the preferences and behaviors of readers when presented with different recommended images (tools that measure different factors of user experience and engagement can be used, as in [22, 23]); ii) the dataset used in this experiment could be expanded to include a more extensive and diverse collection of articles and images to enhance the robustness and generalizability of the findings, and iii) incorporating user feedback and iterative model training could enhance the performance of the VIREO's core models over time. Additionally, considering the evolving nature of the News and Media ecosystem, ongoing research could focus on the adaptability and the ability to recognize emerging content types and trends swiftly. As AI and NLP technologies continue to advance, future work might also explore more advanced techniques for understanding the nuances and context of articles, thus improving the alignment of recommended images. Finally, collaboration with media professionals and content creators could provide valuable insights and feedback for refining image recommendation models to better meet the needs of those in the News and Media industry. These future research directions can contribute to the continued development and enhancement of tools like VIREO in the fast-paced and dynamic world of media and journalism.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented the results of an experiment that assesses the practical efficiency of VIREO's core models in recommending images for real-world articles, emphasizing the value of diversifying image suggestions to enhance user engagement and satisfaction with article-related visuals. This insight holds significant implications for media, content recommendation, and AI, where models like BLIP can stream-

line content creation workflows, align content with audience preferences, and promote user-centric design principles. Future research directions may include exploring user engagement metrics, expanding datasets, and refining models to adapt to evolving content types and trends. Collaboration between AI researchers, media professionals, and content creators will be instrumental in shaping the future of content recommendation and personalization in the dynamic News and Media ecosystem.

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